

Informed Consent Form for Research Study

Principal Investigator: Maheen Arshad

You are being invited to participate in a research study conducted by Maheen Arshad from the Department of Software Engineering at the National University of Computer and Emerging Sciences. Please read this form carefully and give your consent .

* Indicates required question

1. Email Address *

2. Roll# *

3. Full Name *

Purpose of the Study

This study aims to compare the effectiveness of Semantic Business Vocabulary and Rules (SBVR) and Decision Model and Notation (DMN) in the context of software engineering. Your participation will contribute to a better understanding of how these methodologies can be applied in real-world scenarios.

Procedures

If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked to:

- Attend a brief training session on SBVR and DMN.
- Use both methodologies to create and manage business rules as part of a controlled experiment.
- Complete a questionnaire regarding your experiences with each methodology. The entire process is expected to take approximately 2 hours.

Potential Risks :There are no significant risks associated with your participation in this study.

Potential Benefits :While there are no direct benefits to you from participating, your involvement will help improve understanding of business rule methodologies in software engineering education and practice.

Confidentiality :Your responses will be anonymous. All data will be stored securely and will only be reported as aggregated statistics. No individual participant will be identifiable from any report or publication.

Participation and Withdrawal :Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You are free to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Signature : If you are willing to participate in this research, please select "Yes ,I agree to participate option in the space given below and submit it at your early convenience.

4. I agree to participate in the research project under the conditions described above. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes, I agree to participate

No, I do not wish to participate

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